

Quantum versus Classical Bound State Entropy

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. May 27, 2023

In (1), the spatial quantum Shannon's entropy: $-\int dx W_n(x)W_n(x) \ln[W_n(x)W_n(x)]$ ((A)) for a bound state is considered, where $W_n(x)$ is the n th energy eigenstate. In the limit of n very high, quantum entropy is approximated by: $-\int C/v(x) \ln\{C/v(x)\} dx$ ((B)) where $C/v(x)$ is the normalized classical entropy with $.5mv(x)v(x) + V(x) = E_n$. In such a case, $W(x)W(x)$ still has peaks and zero points, but if resolution in the classical world is low, the integral is approximated by the classical $C/v(x)$ which is said to pass through the peaks of $W(x)W(x)$.

In this note, we consider a bound classical particle moving first to the right and then to the left. In such a case, it seems entropy is zero. The argument in (1) is that the time a particle spends in a fixed dx is $dx/v(x)$ and that this should represent an unnormalized probability. We argue this may represent an unnormalized probability for an ensemble of classical systems with the same energy, but different starting points x, t . If one wishes to know the entropy of a single system, we argue it is 0 and not ((B)).

The goal of this note is to find a quantum expression for spatial entropy which tends to 0 in the high n limit. Our approach is to introduce a cut off-length dx which is very small with respect to the system length and is also small in the classical world. Next, $W(x)W(x)$ which has humps and zero values is examined. If the base of any hump is within dx , entropy density is set to 0 within this dx , otherwise it is given by ((A)). As humps become narrower, the entropy becomes smaller as more and more dx units are replaced with 0. In this way, we try to study the change in quantum bound entropy as the system becomes more and more classical with higher E_n values. Thus one has $S(dx, n)$ which may be studied for various dx and n values.

Quantum Bound States

In classical physics, a particle is characterized by an exact x and p (momentum) value, as p is linked with an impulse which may occur at a specific x . In quantum mechanics, a free particle with momentum p has a wavefunction $\exp(ipx)$. This leads to a density of $\exp(ipx)\exp(-ipx)=1$ which maps into a classical probability of each dx having the same weight. $\exp(ipx)$, however, is associated with a wavelength of \hbar/p and within half a wavelength there is uncertainty as to where the particle is, even though momentum p is the same. For a high p for the classical picture, the humps are very narrow compared with resolution lengths.

An issue occurs when one has wavelengths which are of the order of the system length. Given the uncertainty in particle position, one cannot track it using $x(t)$ and there is a scenario in which it is moving to the right, but jumping position within a hump $\cos(px)$, and another in which it has already reached the classical turning point so to speak and is moving in the opposite direction. Thus there is justified interference in such a case. As the wavelength, however, becomes small with respect to the length of the system, there should be no confusing a particle moving to the right with one moving to the left, i.e. there should be no interference between $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-ipx)$ components. The eigenfunctions of the time-independent Schrodinger equation are, however, always real (bound states) and so allow for $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-ipx)$

interference. This seems to suggest an ensemble of states which at some point may not describe a single particle system well.

In general, with a potential, one has a wavefunction $W(x) = \sum_p a(p)\exp(ipx)$ so there are various different wavelengths in the picture. Overall, the various $\exp(ipx)$, $\exp(-ipx)$ terms create a real $W(x)$ which has crests and troughs similar to $\cos(px)$, but with different heights and widths (for example, consider the quantum oscillator). In addition, there is a $p_{rms}(x)$ in the system:

$$\frac{1}{2m} p_{rms}(x) p_{rms}(x) = -\frac{1}{2m} \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} W_n(x) \quad ((1))$$

$$p_{rms}(x) \text{ is also the classical } p(x) \text{ from: } \frac{1}{2m} p(x)p(x) + V(x) = E_n \quad ((2))$$

As n , the energy level in E_n becomes very high, the quantum system is said to become classical. The problem we argue is that the quantum picture includes $\exp(ipx)$ for p and $\exp(-ipx)$ for $-p$ together, while a classical system has p during one interval of time and $-p$ during another. If \hbar/p is small compared with dx , a classical small region within the system, it seems there is no reason for $\exp(ipx)$ to be considered together with $\exp(-ipx)$ i.e. for interference.

Classical Bound State Entropy

In (1) it is suggested that for a bound particle with a fixed dx :

$$dt(x) = dx/v(x) \quad ((3a)) \text{ where } \frac{1}{2m} v(x)v(x) + V(x) = E \quad ((3b))$$

$dx/v(x)$ represents a probability. For a classical bound particle, one would normally consider the system to be deterministic i.e. $x(t)$ and so to have no probability and 0 entropy. The probability ((3a)) might be applicable to an ensemble of bound classical particle systems with different x, t starting points. The problem is that using ((3a)) in Shannon's entropy yields a classical entropy for an ensemble, not for a single physical system.

It is argued in (1) that ((3a)) is a probability function which passes through the peaks of the quantum $W_n(x)W_n(x)$ value when n is very high. Thus $W_n(x)W_n(x)$ also represents an ensemble value it seems, but it is not clear that this describes a single physical system. It would be nice to calculate quantum single particle bound state spatial entropy in such a way that one may see classical features of the system starting to appear. In the next section, we suggest a crude approximate method.

Quantum Bound Entropy to Classical Entropy

We argue that the entropy of a single bound classical particle should be 0 as this is a deterministic system. The quantum low energy levels, however, are very probabilistic due to the wavelength (humps) of $W(x)$ being of the order of the system length. This justifies interference of $+p$, $-p$ terms which yields a real $W(x)$ which exposes the quantum crest trough pattern. One may note that a free particle is described by $\exp(ipx)$. Even though $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$ exhibit crest/trough behaviour, the two dimensional combination maps into 1 i.e. $\exp(ipx)\exp(-ipx)=1$

which exhibits no crests/troughs. Thus it seems it is interference of $+p/-p$ components which reveals the crest/trough behaviour in $W(x)$. There must, however, be a reason for $+p, -p$ to interfere. For low energy levels this is justified, but if the humps of $W(x)W(x)$ become very narrow compared to the system length, it is not clear why one should take interference seriously unless one is considering an ensemble of systems. An ensemble average, however, does not describe a single system.

As a result, we suggest the following crude approach for calculating quantum bound state entropy. First, however, a length dx must be chosen which is small compared to the system length and also very small in the classical world. This dx is then arbitrary, but a similar procedure is used in numerical integration for which one chooses finite width dx values (in some approaches). As a result, one has an entropy $S(dx,n)$. It is possible to test different values of dx to see what differences they yield in S . We suggest:

$$\text{Entropy density} = 0 \quad \text{if } \frac{1}{2m} p_{rms}(x)p_{rms}(x) + V(x) = E_n \quad ((4a))$$

$$\text{Entropy density} = -W(x)W(x) \ln\{W(x)W(x)\} \quad \text{otherwise} \quad ((4b))$$

This leads to an $S(dx, n)$ which should slowly tend to 0 in the large n limit and might describe how the system moves from being quantum mechanical to classical.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that a classical bound system should have 0 entropy, yet using $P(x) = C/v(x)$ where $\frac{1}{2}mv(x)v(x) + V(x) = E$ as in (1) yields a nonzero entropy. We thus suggest that $-\int dx P(x) \ln(P(x))$ may represent the entropy of an ensemble of classical single particle bound states with different initial x,t . One may, however, only be interested in a single system.

A quantum bound state is described by a wavefunction involving the interference of different $\exp(ipx)$ free particle wavefunctions i.e. $W(x) = \text{Sum over } p \ a(p)\exp(ipx)$. Interference is justified for all energy levels if one considers an ensemble of systems, but if one only wishes to study one system, it seems interference of $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-ipx)$ should only occur when $\frac{1}{2} \hbar/p$ is of the order of the system length. If \hbar/p becomes very small relative to the system length, it is not clear why $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-ipx)$ should interfere for a non-ensemble scenario. The time-independent Schrodinger equation may be fine for calculating energy levels, but one needs an clear interpretation of $W_n(x)W_n(x)$ as n becomes high.

In general, $W(x)$ is comprised of crests/troughs which are created through the interference of various $\exp(ipx)$ s. We wish to obtain an expression for spatial quantum entropy density which incorporates classical changes occurring locally in x . Thus we suggest that if $p_{rms}(x)$ given by $\frac{1}{2m} p_{rms}(x)p_{rms}(x) + V(x) = E_n$ yields $\frac{1}{2} \hbar/p_{rms}(x) \leq dx$, then one set entropy density to 0 within this dx . Dx is arbitrary, but chosen to be small with respect to the system size and to be a small value in the classical world. (In numerical integration, a small dx is also chosen and leads to a certain small error in the integral) Otherwise, $-W(x)W(x) \ln\{W(x)W(x)\}$ is used as entropy density. This allows for the crude calculation of $S(dx,n)$ which might show very approximately a change from a quantum to classical picture for a single system.

One may thus calculate $S(dx, n)$ for various dx and n values to see how the entropy eventually becomes 0 with increasing n . The energy density may also show certain x regions becoming classical more quickly than others. Although this approach is very crude, it might shed some light on how quantum bound state entropy slowly disappears for large energy levels.

References

1. Majernick, V and Opatrny, T. Entropic uncertainty relations for a Harmonic Oscillator (1999)
https://www.researchgate.net/publication/231048623_Entropic_uncertainty_relations_for_a_quantum_oscillator